

21.09.2024

RESEARCHER MENTAL HEALTH

OVERVIEW IN R. N. MACEDONIA

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COST ACTION CA19117 - Researcher Mental Health (ReMO)

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What is in the news?

A new Strategy for promotion of mental health with an Action Plan in RN Macedonia (2018-2025) has been adopted by the Ministry of Health. This Strategy includes an overview of the results from the previous Strategy (2005-2012). The decentralization of mental health care resulted in 7 new opened mental health centers, but the process has been stopped. An increasing trend of the capacities of psychiatric hospitals has been observed with a slow reintegration of institutionalized patients into the community. The need for adequate planning of human resources, financing of community mental health, as well as monitoring and evaluation of outlined activities has been highlighted. The new Strategy has several objectives, such as:

1. An accessible, comprehensive and integrated system of mental health services in the community
2. Promotion and protection of human rights of persons with mental disorders and their families
3. Establishing programs for promotion and prevention in the field of mental health care
4. Strengthening the scientific research activities and the information system in the field of mental health care
5. Strengthening the leadership and management in the field of mental health care
6. Strengthening the human resources
7. Improved financing of the mental health care
8. Implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the National Strategy and Action Plan

The new Law on mental health has been adopted by the Government in 2006 (Official Gazette No 71/06) with some amendments and supplements adopted in 2015 (Official Gazette No 150/15). This Law elaborates the basic principles for the protection and promotion of mental health, the rights and obligations of persons with mental illness, the rights and obligations of health institutions and health workers, the procedures for the protection of the rights of persons with mental illness, as well as the supervision of Law enforcement.

What is in the news?

The Institute of Public Health of RN Macedonia annually celebrates the World Mental Health Day. The mental health issue and the celebration of World Mental Health Day has been also put into agenda of WHO Country Office in North Macedonia. Other international organizations or their parts based in RN Macedonia (e.g., UNICEF, UNDP) have also put focus on mental health.

The research activities of the Institute of Occupational Health of RN Macedonia, WHO CC, are strongly oriented towards evaluation of job stress, burnout, job demands, job resources, and other workplace psychosocial factors in different groups of workers.

The Ministry of Health on the official website has published recommendations for the improvement of mental health during pandemic. Official phone lines have been operated in order to help persons with mental health problems in the context of current pandemic.

The National Youth Council of Macedonia (NYCM) recently has published a series of handbooks on youth mental health (e.g., anxiety, depression, stress) (January, 2022).

The mental health issue is usually present at the social media. The interest about the protection and promotion of mental health is increasing within the recent years. The public is concerned about the influence of the societal factors on mental health. There is also an increased worries about the workplace factors causing mental health problems, such as job stress and burnout. The job demands are highlighted, together with financial issues, supervisor support, and reduced possibilities for career promotion as examples of workplace factors causing stress.

What is in the news?

The Law on Scientific-Research Activity regulates the principles, goals, public interest, the realization of scientific research activities, the subjects of scientific research activities and the method of funding of scientific research activities. This Law respects the principles, among others, of inviolability and protection of the person and dignity of man, as well as the protection of intellectual property.

On the 02.12.2021, the National Council for Higher Education and Scientific Research Activity has adopted the work program for the period 2021-2025. The establishment of the National Council for Higher Education and Scientific Research Activity is regulated by the Law on Higher Education (Official Gazette No 82/18).

The National Council has been established for the purposes of ensuring, evaluating, developing and improving quality in higher education and research in the RN Macedonia. One of the principles of work of the National Council is the realization of the constitutionally guaranteed autonomy that includes academic freedom, independent decision-making and management and inviolability of the university. However, the health and safety in academia (including mental health) is usually not spoken in RN Macedonia, both by key stakeholders or in social media.

Recently (March, 2022), the Chair of Occupational Medicine (within the Institute of Occupational Health of RN Macedonia) as a part of the Faculty of Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius, University in Skopje, has initiated foundation of a Committee for Safety and Health at University level that would be responsible for safety and health at work of academia/scientist/researchers (both faculty members and students) at all levels of education and research. The foundation of that Committee is still in progress.

Funding for research and academia

According to the official data, only 0.003% of the Budget of RN Macedonia for 2021 has been planned for scientific research activities (Program for Scientific-Research Activities, Official Gazette No 3/21). The financial resources have been allocated for the following activities: programs for public scientific institutions, national scientific research projects, bilateral scientific research projects, organization of scientific meetings, publishing activities (scientific books), participation of domestic researchers at international scientific meetings, study visits abroad, publication of scientific papers in scientific journals (with impact factor), and scholarships for young scientific and research personnel.

The most significant financier of research activities, from which the highest quality scientific papers arise, are the European funds (e.g., COST, FP6, FP7, H2020). Additionally, institutions from the region and beyond appear to be supporters of research activities in the country.

According to the Ministry of Education and Science, there is an increasing trend in the percentage of GDP that is allocated to research. If in 2018.252 million denars were allocated for research activities, in 2019 there were 295 million denars, in 2020 – 300 million denars, and in 2021 there are over 400 million denars.

There is a change in the funding schemes of scientific research activities through introduction of program and planned funding and continuation of grant funding. The Fund for Innovation and Technological Development in cooperation with the Ministry of Education and Science, through grant funding, has awarded 34 innovation vouchers with a total value of 15 million denars which should encourage the development of science in the country. A total of 17.3 million denars has been awarded for research purposes and development of laboratory resources of scientific and higher education institutions. Additional call is intended for financing the implementation of scientific research projects of public scientific institutions which will receive up to 3 million denars per project.

Persona of the researcher on the career ladder in the country

According to the data of the State Statistics Office, in 2021, a total of 1.976 people acquired the title of Master of Science or Specialist (1.727 - 87.4% Masters and 249 - 12.6% Specialists). The number of Masters and Specialists, compared to 2020, has increased by 12.4%. The participation of women in the total number of people who obtained the scientific degree Master of Science in 2021 was 59.6%.

According to the data of the State Statistics Office, in 2021, 201 people obtained the title of Doctor of Science, which represents an increase of 15.5% compared to 2020. The largest number of people received PhD title in the field of health and social protection (23.4%), followed by 17.4% in social sciences, journalism and information, then business, administration and law (15.9%), arts and humanities with 11.4%, and the rest of the fields have a lower frequency. A total of 115 women defended their doctorate dissertation during 2021, which represents 57.2% of the total number of people who received their PhD title in the same year. The largest percentage of the total number of people who obtained a PhD title (30.8%), perform their professional activities in the field of education.

According to the data of the State Statistics Office, the number of professors and associates in higher education institutions in the academic year 2021/2022 was 4.556. Of the total number of professors and associates, 3.182 (69.8%) were professors and 1.374 (30.2%) were teaching assistants. The number of female professors and associates in the academic year 2021/2022 was 2.258 (49.6%).

Academic system in the country

Currently there are both public and private accredited universities in RN Macedonia.

Of all, 7 universities are public, and 9 are private. Additionally, there are 11 private institutions for higher education.

According to the data of the State Statistical Office, obtained on the basis of received reports, the number of graduated students at higher vocational schools and faculties in 2021 was 7.753 (58.8% female students), an increase of 12.2% compared to 2020. Of the total number of graduates, 6.528 (84.2%) were full-time students, while 1.225 (15.8%) were part-time students. A total of 5.630 students (72.6%) graduated at public higher vocational schools and faculties, 2022 (26.1%) at private ones, while 101 (1.3%) at religion faculties. The most of the students have graduated at the University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje - 2.656 (34.3%).

In 2020, 2.276 enterprises organised at least one type of continuing vocational training. Internal courses for continuing vocational training existed in 1.327 enterprises, representing 23.7% of the total number of enterprises, while external courses were carried out in 30.2% or 1.689 enterprises. Continuing vocational training was most frequent in enterprises with more than 250 employees, or 66.3% of these enterprises organised at least one type of continuing vocational training. State-owned enterprises that conducted continuing vocational training accounted for 48.5% of the total number of enterprises in state ownership.

The Senate of the University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje, at the meeting held on 28.10.2021, adopted a Decision to establish the Center for Advanced Interdisciplinary Research at the University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje. This Center presents a new instrument of the University with an aim to strengthen internationalization and international cooperation. The mission is to connect scientists and researchers who work and create in the world and who are born in the country, to establish cooperation with the University, to create a network with our scientific staff and young researchers and through synergy to develop scientific interdisciplinary cores in different areas, which will contribute to improving the visibility of the University in the international scientific research ecosystem. The vision of the Center is to be a hub for scientists born in our country, who want to network and establish cooperation with the University.

Career track for researcher in the country

In RN Macedonia, researchers must complete the first cycle of studies before pursuing their career path. Scholarships are available to students enrolled in the first year of this cycle at all universities. Additionally, faculties have decided to cover half of the enrollment fee for students whose single parent exercises parental rights, provided they meet the necessary criteria.

After completing their first cycle of studies, the path for a researcher is determined by their faculty. They can choose to enroll in a second cycle of studies (postgraduate studies) or immediately begin a third cycle of studies (doctoral studies). Each faculty operates with the European credit transfer system, which determines whether a student could progress to the second or third cycle, based on the number of earned credits. For example, completing the first cycle of studies at the Faculty of Medicine earns the title of Doctor of Medicine. The maximum number of credits in most faculties is 240, but that number at the Faculty of Medicine is 360.

The second and third cycle of studies are multidisciplinary and open, with the organization of the second cycle following the European credit transfer system. These studies emphasize international cooperation with academic institutions from across Europe and beyond, promoting academic exchange and mobility for both students and teaching staff.

The second cycle of study program lasts for two years or 120 credits/points, which follows the European system of transfer of points. Although not all faculties offer scholarships, some faculties in RN Macedonia award scholarships to their students enrolled in the second cycle of studies. The teaching is done through modular courses, which allows longer preparation and the invitation of external guest lecturers to enhance the academic standard. The language of teaching and all activities is Macedonian.

The program is created based on certain premises. The number of credits per semester must be at least 30 (60 in a year). One credit/point takes 25–30 hours of work, and 60 credits require 1500 to 1800 hours of work in teaching and individual work. The total number of hours of active teaching must not be less than 600 hours per school year, with at least 20 hours per week. Lectures should account for 25% of the total teaching hours. At least 50% of the credits are allocated to the completion of the master's thesis, including elective courses, research forum, and integrative workshop.

Career track for researcher in the country

In the last semester, active teaching is only for the research work related to the preparation of the master's thesis. The master's thesis is the final part of the academic university studies in the second cycle. To enroll in the second cycle, one must have knowledge of the English language (with a certificate from the Faculty of Philology or an international certificate such as TOEFL, FCE, CAE) and basic computer skills. The Master's program is accredited by the Accreditation Decision and the Minister of Education's Decision for the start of the program.

The re-accreditation project adheres to the Law on Higher Education and the Rulebook for enrollment and studying in the third cycle of studies - doctoral studies. The Doctor of Science title is earned through independent scientific research in collaboration with a mentor and preparation of a doctoral thesis. These multidisciplinary academic studies are open to different study programs. Doctoral studies follow the European credit transfer system and enable students with 360 credits to improve their competencies as independent researchers and earn the title of Doctor of Science with 180 additional credits.

Foreign nationals are also eligible for enrollment in accordance with the Law on Higher Education and Regulations. The purpose of doctoral studies is to advance scientific research, artistic and professional work, transfer knowledge to new generations, develop new technologies and projects, and internationalize the University.

Doctoral studies are organized and coordinated in the University School for Doctoral Studies of the University with the participation of the faculties, scientific institutes of the University and public scientific institutions - affiliated members of the University.

The University School provides: criteria for uniform scientific research quality of doctoral studies in all scientific research areas, rational and optimal use of scientific research and other personnel, as well as the available research infrastructure, the possibility of organizing interdisciplinary studies and coordination of studies

Doctoral studies are carried out by faculties, scientific institutes, and public scientific institutions - associate members of the University, in accordance with the Law on Higher Education, study programs and Regulations. Doctoral studies can also be realized jointly by two or more units. The University, in accordance with the Law on Higher Education, Regulations and the act for organizing a joint study program.

Career track for researcher in the country

It is possible to participate in doctoral studies in cooperation with one or more universities, either in RN Macedonia or abroad, after the program has been accredited. These studies can be completed in Macedonian, English, or both languages. They are overseen by the University Expert Council for Doctoral Studies, which consists of eleven members, including the vice rector for teaching and the vice-rector for science. Other members include representatives from various scientific research areas, scientific institutes, and public scientific institutions associated with the university. The members are selected by the University Senate and serve for a term of three years or until new members are elected.

The doctoral thesis is an original scientific paper that demonstrates the student's independence and suitability for future research work. In the field of arts, the thesis consists of a theoretical part and a public performance, such as an exhibition, concert, or theater performance.

The final title of the thesis must not differ significantly from the working title. The content of the thesis should align with the published working title of the doctoral project and must be written according to the standards set by the Professional Council for Doctoral Studies.

In programs conducted in Macedonian, the thesis must be written in Macedonian, but it can also be written in English. For English-language programs, the thesis must be written in English, with a library copy also submitted in Macedonian. In exceptional cases when the program is conducted in a language other than Macedonian or English, the thesis must be written in the appropriate language with a translation into Macedonian. An abstract in both Macedonian and another language is also required and should follow the standards established by the Professional Council for Doctoral Studies.

Upon successful completion of the program, the candidate earns the scientific title of Doctor of Science or Doctor of Arts, depending on the field of study. This title is defined by the study program in which the candidate completed their doctoral studies.

Career track for researcher in the country

In the country there are neither specific tenure track systems nor data about the distribution of permanent and temporary staff at different career stages. On the other hand, there are principal performance evaluation/assessment systems for career advancement at each University in RN Macedonia.

Funds are available for scientific research projects, awarded through a competitive process. The Rector's Office announces the competition at the start of the winter semester. The competition includes information about the contents, deadlines, procedures for implementation, total budget, application requirements, and final report elements. Users may only apply for funding once per year, up to a maximum of 30% of the science fund's total funds for the current year. Universities have the right to monitor the allocation of funds, using methods such as internal or external auditors or other experts, as determined by the University's Rector.

Researchers employed by the University with teaching-scientific or scientific titles, associate titles, and doctoral assistants are eligible for financial resources if they have published a paper in the Web of Science databases of Clarivate Analytics or Scopus of Elsevier. These resources are awarded through a competition announced by the Commission for Science and are granted once per published paper. The University can award financial resources for up to 20 scientific papers from each scientific area per academic year. If a paper has multiple authors, it is up to the authors to decide on the division of financial resources.

There is no specific definition of early career researchers (ECR) and the specific programs of support and training are developed in each University. Unfortunately, there is evident brain drain from the country due to reduced possibilities for researchers.

Climate around mental health and well-being – in general and in academia

According to Dr Anne Johansen, WHO's Special Representative to North Macedonia, the prevalence of mental illness in North Macedonia is high and expected to increase due to the COVID-19 pandemic and its socioeconomic consequences. In the wake of the pandemic, the need to improve public mental health services was more evident than ever and the aim should be to put mental health and well-being at the heart of the national health system as a key to recovery from the COVID-19 emergency.

As stated by the data from Mental Health Atlas from 2020, the burden of mental health disorders in North Macedonia is estimated as 1360.1 DALYs per 100 000 population, with age-standardized suicide mortality rate 7.15 per 100 000 population.

In terms of the burden of adolescent disease, depression is considered to be the third leading cause, while suicide is the second leading cause of death among young people aged 15-29 years.

To increase the level of general public awareness for mental health, several nationwide campaigns, organized in form of initiatives, public calls, workshops, research studies or procuring of counselling centers, from different associations, were conducted.

Every year, in association with the Red Cross organization, World Mental Health day (10 October) is celebrated.

The Macedonian Association for Applied Psychology (MAAP), together with the Association of Young Psychologists (TRINOVA), in 2020, formed an initiative called "Together FOR mental health", which was focused on the mental health needs of students, teachers, and parents during COVID-19. The initiative aimed to protect and promote the mental health of the citizens of the Republic of N. Macedonia, initiate positive social changes in all areas where psychologists work and promote the importance of (applied) psychology especially in conditions of sociopolitical, social, and health crises.

Also, in 2020, UNICEF conducted a study about the mental health of adolescents and their caregivers during the Covid-19 pandemic in North Macedonia, which aimed to collect data on the sociodemographic characteristics and mental health of adolescents and their caregivers in the context of the established restrictive measures as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic in the country.

Climate around mental health and well-being – in general and in academia

In 2022, UNICEF announced a call for action for immediate mental health support in schools to answer the mental health needs of children and young people. The campaign emphasized the role of school management to ensure that school support staff including psychologists, pedagogues and special educators are empowered and fully dedicated to support children and colleagues during the school year.

UNICEF, in 2022, also, organized a mental health workshop for social protection of frontline workers that provided evidence of the negative effect of poverty on mental health in North Macedonia. Workers interested in learning how to cope with stress and build resilience shared their experiences with stress caused by daily dealings with complex cases of poverty and related adversities.

As part of a joint European Union and Council of Europe programme, in November 2022, a first ever training session, for professionals working in prisons, was organized to enhance their knowledge on mental healthcare management in prisons. Eight doctors and medical personnel, ten prison officers working in six penitentiary institutions in North Macedonia, along with Staff from the Ombudsman's National Prevention Mechanism and the External Oversight Mechanism units attended this training programme.

The mental health issue among working population is special interest of the Institute of Occupational Health of North Macedonia, WHO Collaborating Center. During the last decade, the Institute realized few very important research activities at international level. One of them is EU 7th FWP project "Improving quality and safety in the hospital: The link between organizational culture, burnout, and quality of care (ORCAB)", aiming to benchmark the organizational and individual factors that impact on quality of care and patient safety, and design bottom-up interventions that both increase quality of care and physician wellbeing.

Other important project, coordinated by the Institute, WHO CC, Skopje is SEE survey "Job Stress in Health Workers (HWs) during Covid-19 pandemics", with more than 4500 respondents from 10 SEE countries. The objectives of the study were: to obtain data about burnout and job engagement dimensions, job satisfaction, and job demands/resources in HWs during COVID-19 pandemic and to compare the findings between SEE countries.

Climate around mental health and well-being – in general and in academia

In the frame of educational and promotional activities, in June–July 2020, within the collaboration with Organization of Employers, the Institute organized a webinar on “Mental health in workers during the COVID-19 pandemics” suggesting possible strategies for tackling mental health issue at the workplace in order to promote mental health, wellbeing, and resiliency.

Within the collaboration with the Macedonian Medical Association, a paper “Mental health in workers during COVID-19 pandemic” in the Doctors’ Gazette, was published (August, 2020).

Macedonian Society of Occupational Medicine, with participation of the team of the Institute, in collaboration with the UK Society of Occupational Medicine organized an International webinar: Job resources and relationships with job engagement and job satisfaction, in April, 2023.

IN June 2023, the Institute of Occupational Health of RNM, Faculty of Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius, University in Skopje and Andrija Stampar School of Public Health, University of Zagreb, Croatia organized an International Webinar “Mental Health and Work” with more than 100 participants from 7 SEE countries. This webinar was focused on different elements and aspects of mental health and work and should contribute to the increased awareness and knowledge on the issue among OH professionals in SEE. The issue on researcher mental health was also noted.

Within the campaign “Promotion of health and safety at workplace for Health Workers”, the Institute, also, prepared a brochure about “Prevention of stress at work among Health Workers”.

In academia settings, most of the faculties in North Macedonia do not have a psychologist at all, but there are rare exceptions.

In 2018, University “St. Kliment Ohridski”- Bitola founded the first psychological counseling center for students, with main objective to promote mental health among students by developing healthy lifestyles, fostering resentment, and assisting in resolving current and developmental problems. Students have the opportunity for individual or group psychological counseling, psycho-educational workshops, as well as workshops for the development of life skills. Currently, there are 2 centers within the University, one in Faculty of Security- Skopje, and second one in the Kredo center in Bitola.

Climate around mental health and well-being – in general and in academia

During the COVID-19 pandemics, professors from the same University provided free call center for all students who would like to discuss with psychologist regarding the situation with pandemic. At the end of 2020, they also organized free webinar on topic “Mental health of students during COVID - 19”. This webinar was supported by the National Platform of the Chamber of Psychologists.

Several non-governmental organizations (the National Youth Council of Macedonia, Youth Can, Psihesko and S.H.A.R.E.) undertake many different activities related to the mental health of the youth in academia.

For the academic staff and researchers, these types of services are not provided. The health and safety in academia (including mental health) is usually not spoken in RN Macedonia, both by key stakeholders or in social media.

Recently (March, 2022), the Chair of Occupational Medicine (within the Institute of Occupational Health of RN Macedonia) as a part of the Faculty of Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius, University in Skopje, has initiated foundation of a Committee for Occupational Safety and Health at University level, that would be responsible for safety and health at work of academia/scientist/researchers (both faculty members and students), at all levels of education and research. The foundation of the Committee is still in progress.

The interests about the researcher mental health in North Macedonia are still on a low level.

This issue has been neglected by policy makers, occupational health and safety representatives, as well as by the working population in general. There is an urgent need to put the researcher mental health on the agenda at all levels - community, institutional, and policy level.

At the Faculty of Medicine in Skopje, “Job stress and burnout” exists, as an elective subject, aimed at all undergraduate study programs. The issue is also included in the lectures for the students of the postgraduate Master of Public Health program.

Mental health support and service systems

The mental health system in North Macedonia is organized in inpatient and outpatient care facilities. The inpatient care is provided in four mental health hospitals and eight psychiatric units in general hospitals, as well as a special facility dedicated for children and adolescents.

The outpatient care is organized in 20 hospital-attached mental health facilities, 32 mental health day care facilities, but zero “community-based/non-hospital” mental health facilities.

According to the Mental Health Atlas, the total number of mental health professionals is 659, from which 179 psychiatrists and 376 nurses in the country as of 2020.

In line with the removal of barriers to providing and accessing mental health resources within the reforms from 2000 to 2008, supported by WHO and the Ministry of Health, North Macedonia’s mental health care moved out of hospitals and into community mental health centers, providing the need to remove patients from the negative conditions of hospital-based mental health units.

Also, in 2020, RECOVER-E (LaRge-scale implementation of COMMunity based mental health care for people with seVere and Enduring mental ill health in EuROPE) project for the Central and Eastern European region was conducted, which aimed to implement and evaluate multidisciplinary community mental health teams in five countries in the region, including North Macedonia.

The intervention consisted of the introduction of a new service delivery model, consisting of community-based recovery-oriented care delivered by trained multidisciplinary community mental health teams.

In North Macedonia, there are 2 helplines that support a range of mental health or behavioral health concerns, providing immediate mental health support to the public for free.

According to the experts in the field, to further develop the community mental health system, it is necessary to provide continuous education of the staff at the mental health centres and consolidate their work throughout the country, as well as continuous education of primary health care professionals is needed to improve knowledge about mental illness, educate people with mental illness and their families, and destigmatize mental illness.

In North Macedonia, the insurance fully covers mental health services and psychotropic medicines. with the country spending 7.3% of its total health expenditure on mental health and 19.8% on mental health hospitals of total Government mental health expenditure.

Workplace of academia, employment

According to the Law on Higher Education, the procedure of promotion in teaching-scientific, teaching-professional, scientific, and associate titles finalizes with an establishment of a full-time employment relationship between the promoted researcher and the higher education institution. The employment contract is signed for the duration of period for which the person is promoted in the respective title. The promoted persons with realized employment have certain rights and obligations from the employment relationship in accordance with this and other laws (Law on Labor Relations) and collective agreement.

Only full professors have a permanent employment until the retirement, their title remains for life, and then they can be engaged in the third cycle - doctoral studies at the University.

The Law on scientific research activity gives overview of the duties of researchers who are selected in the institutions for performing research and they are promoted in scientific titles, such as: scientific associate, senior scientific associate and scientific advisor. The persons promoted in a scientific title establish an employment contract and have rights and obligations from an employment relationship in accordance with this and other laws.

With the promotion in a scientific title, the researcher establishes an employment relationship for the time for which he was selected (for 5 years). During the promotion, if the person who was previously elected in a scientific title is proposed for promotion in a higher title and if during that vote the person is not promoted in the higher title, a vote is taken again for election in the existing title in which he/she was previously elected. If the person who is not selected in the title, the employment contract is then terminated.

Workplace of academia, employment

Paid and unpaid leave

At the request, of a person selected in a teaching-scientific, teaching-professional, scientific, and associate title, every five years, the higher education institution can grant him a paid leave of up to one year (sabbatical year), or unpaid leave of up to three years for the purpose of professional development, research in the relevant scientific, artistic field or for a stay in a relevant institution, during which his/her responsibilities in teaching are redistributed. If the stay is at one of the first hundred universities ranked on the last published list of the following institutions: Institute of Higher Education at Shanghai Jiao Tong University, US News and Report *и* Times Higher Education Supplement – World University Ranking, in addition to paid leave, the Ministry in charge of higher education reimburses the costs of accommodation, food, health insurance and travel expenses, if they are not reimbursed by the institution where the stay is carried out or by another institution.

The issue of health insurance is regulated, as it is for all citizens of the Republic of North Macedonia, through the Law on Health Insurance and the Law on Health Care. There is no specific type of health or social insurance for researchers. It depends on their employment status.

This also applies to the issue of health care. Researchers are included in the health care system, like other employees. An example of organized health care for students and employees of the University can be mentioned: For health care for the students of the first cycle, as well as for the students of the second and third cycle (master's and doctoral students), as well as the employees of the University, Skopje, in charge is the Health Institution – Student Polyclinic of the University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje. According to article 121 of the Statute of UKIM, within the system of health care, for all students and employees of the University, a University Polyclinic can be established. The university polyclinic performs health activities in preventive-primary, specialist-consultative health care, diagnostics, etc.

Policy view on mental health/ well-being

Several laws in the Republic of North Macedonia cover this matter: according to the **Law on Higher Education**, the basic principles of higher education include respect for human rights and freedoms and guaranteeing the principle of equity and protection against discrimination, and the **Law on scientific-research activity** highlights in its principles the freedom and autonomy of research and creativity and the inviolability and protection of the person and the dignity of man.

The prevention and prohibition of discrimination, the forms and types of discrimination, the procedures for protection against discrimination, as well as the composition and work of the Commission for Prevention and Protection against Discrimination are regulated by a special law, the Law on Prevention and Protection from Discrimination. This law applies to all natural and legal persons and is applied by all state authorities, authorities of local self-government units, legal persons with public powers and all other legal and natural persons in several fields including: education, science and sports.

This law prohibits any discrimination based on race, skin color, origin national or ethnic origin, sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, belonging to a marginalized group, language, citizenship, social origin, education, religion or religious belief, political belief, other belief, disability, age, marital or marital status, property status, health status, personal quality and social status or any other basis.

The Code of Ethics of the University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje, which specifically refers to employees from the University (including researchers), has identical views as the Law, expressed as ethically unacceptable behaviors. Different forms of harassment among members of the university community, such as general harassment and sexual harassment, are specifically singled out in the Code of Ethics.

Policy view on mental health/ well-being

The Law on Labor Relations, which regulates the labor relations between workers and employers that are established by concluding an employment contract, sets out a separate article that refers to the Prohibition of Discrimination (in which, in addition to the above, the prohibition of discrimination also refers to membership in the union). This Law states the prohibition of direct and indirect discrimination and lists them as forms of unacceptable behavior at the workplace - harassment and gender harassment, as well as psychological harassment at the workplace (mobbing).

The Law on Protection against Harassment at the Workplace regulates the rights, obligations and responsibilities of employers and employees in relation to the prevention of psychological and sexual harassment at the workplace and the place of work, measures and procedures for protection against harassment at the workplace, and other issues related to the prevention and protection from harassment in the workplace. The purpose of the Law is to prevent and protect against psychological and sexual harassment at the workplace, i.e. the place of work and ensuring a healthy working environment. This law applies to employers, employees, candidates for employment, as well as to persons engaged with contracts, who participate in the work of the employer. According to this Law, the employer is obliged to provide the employee with work at the workplace in a healthy working environment under conditions that ensure respect for his dignity, integrity and health. The law prescribes a procedure for protection against harassment at the workplace with the employer, and the possibility of judicial protection.

In the Law on Prevention and Protection from Discrimination, harassment and sexual harassment are specifically defined, as unwanted behavior or on discriminatory grounds or of a sexual nature, but with the same purpose or consequence, violation of dignity or creation of a threatening, hostile, humiliating or intimidating environment, approach or practice.

Policy view on mental health/ well-being

The Law on Mental Health regulates the basic principles for the protection, promotion and advancement of mental health, the rights and obligations of persons with mental illness, the rights and obligations of health institutions and health workers and associates, the procedure for the protection of the rights of persons with mental illness, as well as the supervision of law enforcement. Special reference is made to the rights of persons with mental illness by which the personality, dignity and privacy of every person with mental illness must be respects. A person with a mental illness has the right of protection from any form of harassment, humiliation and abuse and must not be discriminated against because of his mental health condition.

The statute of the University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje, regulates and guarantees equality, non-discrimination and inclusiveness, and in which articles protection against discrimination is provided, and guarantees for equal opportunities for women and men at the University are provided. The strategy of the University "St. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje 2019-2023, foresees the principle of equality in teaching-scientific activity and, together with the principle of responsibility and compliance with the highest possible standards, encourages active cooperation of University with higher education, scientific and other related institutions in other countries.

University "Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje (UKIM) adopted the UKIM Gender Equality Plan, 2022, which follows the main European strategic documents related to gender equality: The Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025; European Commission: Guidelines for Gender Equality Plans; European Institute for Gender Equality: Gender Equality in Academia and Research, GEAR Tool.

Stakeholders and policies

Recognition and improvement of the status of researchers

The Government (Ministry of Education and Science) adopted the Law on Scientific-Research Activity (Official Gazette No 46/2008) with its amendments (Official Gazette No 46/2008, 103/2008, 24/2011, 80/2012, 24/2013, 147/2013, 41/2014, 145/2015, 154/2015, 30/2016, 53/2016, 257/2020) that regulates the principles, goals, public interest, the realization of scientific research activities, the subjects of scientific research activities and the method of funding of scientific research activities.

The Government also adopted the Law on Higher Education (Official Gazette No 82/2018) which regulates the basic principles of higher education including respect for human rights and freedoms and guaranteeing the principle of equity and protection against discrimination.

The University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje with its' Statute regulates and guarantees equality, non-discrimination and inclusiveness, and in which articles protection against discrimination is provided, and guarantees for equal opportunities for women and men at the University are provided. The strategy of the University "St. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje 2019-2023, foresees the principle of equality in teaching-scientific activity and, together with the principle of responsibility and compliance with the highest possible standards, encourages active cooperation of University with higher education, scientific and other related institutions in other countries.

Stakeholders and policies

The University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius" in Skopje adopted an Action Plan for the realization of Strategy (2019–2023) with several main objectives, including: modernization of study programs with closer cooperation with the business community through realization of joint projects; improvement of teaching conditions through investments in modernization of premises, equipment and application of new digital technologies; strengthening the potential of teaching staff by supporting their professional development and acquisition of abilities and skills; promotion of international cooperation; provision of professional and administrative support for greater mobility of teaching staff and students; increasing the participation of staff in international organizations; providing greater funds for scientific research work from own sources and from the state; or introducing a service to support the commercialization of research results. Some of the proposed activities within the Action Plan are as follows: establishment of career centers at the units (Faculties) of the University; possibilities of developing forms of further qualification and retraining for the needs of the business sector; development of incubators, accelerators and implementation of joint projects; formation of interdisciplinary hubs; financial support of published scientific papers in publications with an impact factor; involving the best students in the activities of scientific research projects; or requests for an increase in the percentage of the budget for the development of teaching and research staff at the University and the employment of young research staff.

The Government (Ministry of Labor and Social Policy) adopted the Law on Health and Safety at Work (Official Gazette No 92/07) (and subsequent amendments) which regulates the measures for safety and health at work, the obligations of the employer and the rights and obligations of employees in the field of safety and health at work, as well as preventive measures against occupational risks, the reduction of risk factors for accidents at work, information, consultation, training of workers and their representatives and their participation in planning and taking measures for safety and health at work.

Stakeholders and policies

Advocating for the mental health and well-being of researchers

The Ministry of Health on the official website has published recommendations for the improvement of mental health during pandemic. Official phone lines have been operated in order to help persons with mental health problems in the context of current pandemic.

The mental health issue and the celebration of World Mental Health Day has been also put into agenda of WHO Country Office in North Macedonia. Other international organizations or their parts based in RN Macedonia (e.g., UNICEF, UNDP) have also put focus on mental health.

The research activities of the Institute of Occupational Health of RN Macedonia, WHO CC, are strongly oriented towards evaluation of job stress, burnout, job demands, job resources, and other workplace psychosocial factors in different groups of workers.

The National Youth Council of Macedonia (NYCM) recently has published a series of handbooks on youth mental health (e.g., anxiety, depression, stress) (January, 2022).

Every year, in association with the Red Cross organization, World Mental Health day (10 October) is celebrated.

As part of a joint European Union and Council of Europe programme, in November 2022, a first ever training session, for professionals working in prisons, was organized to enhance their knowledge on mental healthcare management in prisons.

An important project, coordinated by the Institute of Occupational Health of RNM, WHO CC, Skopje is SEE survey “Job Stress in Health Workers (HWs) during Covid-19 pandemics”, with more than 4500 respondents from 10 SEE countries. The objectives of the study were: to obtain data about burnout and job engagement dimensions, job satisfaction, and job demands/resources in HWs during COVID-19 pandemic and to compare the findings between SEE countries.

Stakeholders and policies

In the frame of educational and promotional activities, in June-July 2020, within the collaboration with Organization of Employers, the Institute organized a webinar on “Mental health in workers during the COVID-19 pandemics” suggesting possible strategies for tackling mental health issue at the workplace in order to promote mental health, wellbeing, and resiliency.

Within the collaboration with the Macedonian Medical Association, a paper “Mental health in workers during COVID-19 pandemic” in the Doctors’ Gazette, was published (August, 2020).

Macedonian Society of Occupational Medicine, with participation of the team of the Institute, in collaboration with the UK Society of Occupational Medicine organized an International webinar: Job resources and relationships with job engagement and job satisfaction, in April, 2023.

In June 2023, the Institute of Occupational Health of RNM, Faculty of Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius, University in Skopje and Andrija Stampar School of Public Health, University of Zagreb, Croatia organized an International Webinar “Mental Health and Work” with more than 100 participants from 7 SEE countries. This webinar was focused on different elements and aspects of mental health and work and should contribute to the increased awareness and knowledge on the issue among OH professionals in SEE. The issue on researcher mental health was also noted.

Within the campaign “Promotion of health and safety at workplace for Health Workers”, the Institute, also, prepared a brochure about “Prevention of stress at work among Health Workers”.

In 2018, University “St. Kliment Ohridski”- Bitola founded the first psychological counseling center for students, with main objective to promote mental health among students by developing healthy lifestyles, fostering resentment, and assisting in resolving current and developmental problems.

During the COVID-19 pandemics, professors from the same University provided free call center for all students who would like to discuss with psychologist regarding the situation with pandemic. At the end of 2020, they also organized free webinar on topic “Mental health of students during COVID - 19”. This webinar was supported by the National Platform of the Chamber of Psychologists.

At the Faculty of Medicine in Skopje, “Job stress and burnout” exists, as an elective subject, aimed at all undergraduate study programs. The issue is also included in the lectures for the students of the postgraduate Master of Public Health program.

Euraxess centers as hubs for supporting researchers' mobility and career

The search for Euraxess Centers in RN Macedonia on the official Euraxess website shows four centers in RN Macedonia (three Euraxess Centers and one Bridgehead Organisation): Goce Delcev University - Stip, University of Information Science and Technology "St. Paul the Apostle" Ohrid, University St. Kliment Ohridski - Bitola, and Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts as a Bridgehead Organisation.

Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts and the Center for Computer Sciences and Information Technologies organized a two-day event (22-23.09.2017), financially supported by the European Commission through the EURAXESS ENCIRCLE project. The EURAXESS ENCIRCLE project aimed to improve research opportunities in R.N. Macedonia through the increased development of inter-sectoral cooperation, developing skills for planning research careers, establishing a network for collecting and transferring research experiences, and improving the mobility of researchers.

The conference, which was intended for students, scientists and researchers from all scientific disciplines, focused on promoting science and research, inter-sectoral mobility and mobility in general, including scientific presentations on various topics and professional development activities by distinguished scientists, researchers, entrepreneurs, innovators, and other individuals and groups interested in research. It was a platform of open dialogue between researchers, students and industry in all areas of science, engineering and innovation, and aimed to support researchers in their careers and encourage industry to invest in research (R&D).

Source: <http://manu.edu.mk/>

Euraxess centers as hubs for supporting researchers' mobility and career

The Goce Delcev University (UGD) in Stip has been profiled as a higher-education institution that focuses on the students, their needs and ideas. The attention is directed completely on the creation of knowledge and possibilities by providing quality education, innovation, digitalization and development of an intellectual potential for both home and global challenges. The UGD is a highly regarded institution in the field of higher-education, which provides quality education by offering different study-programmes by various faculties and attracts a large number of students from Macedonia and abroad. The university conducts an annual admission of students on its campuses for first, second and third cycle of university studies and professional studies.

UGD has been actively contributing to the creation of modern and complete conditions for scientific and research work that will satisfy the needs of the academic community, but also of the business community as well which requires modern resources, technologies and innovative solutions. For this aim, UGD has contemporary fitted laboratories and centres that constitute the infrastructure that enables the scientific and research activity, while the academic knowledge and education is being conducted through the available programmes of the third cycle doctoral studies in various fields.

Source: <https://www.ugd.edu.mk/en/home/>

Euraxess centers as hubs for supporting researchers' mobility and career

CAREERS

The University of Information Science and Technology (UIST) “St. Paul the Apostle”, is a higher education state institution located in Ohrid. UIST is committed to providing excellence in education and research in the field of information sciences and technology. At UIST are offered innovative contemporary study programs based on best practices of instruction used in some of the leading universities in USA, Europe and Australia. The programs are designed to meet the needs of the new generation of ICT professionals, allowing our students enough space for specialization and pursuit of their individual interests. The international outreach of the university results in UIST having a multicultural student population from a wide variety of countries, along with domestic students. Based on the established relations with other universities and ICT companies, as part of the student exchange programs, UIST gives its students an opportunity of taking a few months during their studies for sponsored staying and studying at designated universities and/or ICT companies in USA and Europe. Students also have the opportunity for participating at several competitions for computer programmers, where the best contestants are awarded with valuable prizes and public promotion, thus enhancing their future career prospects. This is through a strong cooperation which is fostered by UIST with the ICT sector.

On 10 November 2023, on the World Science Day for Peace and Development 2023 Theme: Building Trust in Science, the University of Information Science and Technology (UIST) St. Paul the Apostle signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the University of Library Studies and Information Technologies (ULSIT) from Sofia, Bulgaria. With the partners from Bulgaria, UIST will work on joint research activities and projects, mobility and exchange of faculty staff and students, and development of joint study programs.

UIST has established partnerships with some industry leading IT companies and agencies, both national and international. Besides these collaborations with IT entities, the University collaborates with other institutions from the social sphere and other interdisciplinary areas where information science can find its applications. Through these collaborations, UIST becomes a leader in the efforts to merge the business sector with the academia, and to bring companies closer to students since their earliest times at UIST. This opens the doors to excellent opportunities for student internships, project work, and potential employment within these companies and beyond.

Source: <http://uist.edu.mk/>

Euraxess centers as hubs for supporting researchers' mobility and career

CAREERS

University St. Kliment Ohridski - Bitola (UKLO) has a specific heterogeneous, educational offer which covers a variety of scientific disciplines and educates profiles compatible with the requirements of the current labor market. It is represented by 48 study programs for I cycle studies (undergraduate), 57 for II cycle studies (postgraduate) (of which 9 specialist) and 20 study programs for III cycle studies (PhD studies). The key words in the management of University policy and strategy are: modern, flexible study programs, transparent organizational structure, organizational chart, dynamic management of human resources, active policy of integration into the University environment, creation of strong relations between University and economy, support of new initiatives, emphasis on internationalization, implementing a culture of quality in all spheres of university activity.

UKLO directly or through its units establishes, nurtures, and develops cooperation relations with numerous higher education and scientific institutions from the countries in the Region, the EU member states and more broadly at the global level. Cooperation, on a bilateral and multilateral level, is based on signing cooperation agreements with foreign universities, but also with other institutions, associations and foundations whose interests touch issues related to higher education and scientific research activities. The international cooperation of UKLO is realized through the forms of bilateral, multilateral and project activity, centrally and at the level of units, within the framework of international projects and programs, such as ERASMUS+. The activities are related to the teaching-educational activity through the projects for the improvement of the teaching process, but also with the scientific-research, through the international research and projects for the wider community. UKLO is a signatory to the Charter of Universal Academic Rights and Freedoms – Magna Charta Universitatum.

UKLO's cooperation with the environment (i.e., the economic and public sector) consists of a set of specific activities that have an educational, practical and developmental dimension and are aimed at promoting a sustainable partnership, that is, a significant synergy between the academic and socio-economic spheres.

These relationships are multidirectional: they influence the creation of new and modification of existing curricula in order for students to acquire the necessary skills and knowledge in function of the needs of the labor market, and on the other hand, economic and non-profit entities have the opportunity to use the research and application potentials that the University has, and students have the opportunity to use grants and scholarships from the industry, but also to reach the real, economic world, through practical trainings and internships.

Source: <https://uklo.edu.mk/>

Equity, diversity, inclusion, accessibility in academia

Articles 16–21 of the Statute of the University of Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje, already regulate and guarantee equity, non-discrimination, and inclusiveness. Within this document, the protection against discrimination is provided, and guarantees for equal opportunities for women and men at the University are highlighted. The Strategy of the University Ss. Cyril and Methodius in Skopje 2019–2023, foresees the principle of equity in teaching–scientific activity and, together with the principle of responsibility and compliance with the highest possible standards, encourages active cooperation of UKIM with higher education, scientific and other related institutions in other countries.

In 2019, R.N. Macedonia published its own gender equity index with a score of 62 points. According to the analysis of the European Institute for Gender Equity, R.N. Macedonia is slightly below the European Union average of 67.4 points. This puts the country in 16th place compared to EU countries.

National culture

Power distance

With a very high score of 90, North Macedonia is a nation where power holders are very distant in society. People in this society accept a hierarchical order in which everybody has a place, and which needs no further justification. Hierarchy is seen as reflecting inherent inequalities, and the different distribution of power justifies the fact that power holders have more benefits than the less powerful in society. The discrepancy between the less and the more powerful people leads to a great importance of status symbols.

Individualism

At a score of 40, North Macedonia is a collectivist culture. This is evident in the early integration and close, long-term commitment to a strong, cohesive 'in-group'. These societies foster strong relationships where everyone takes responsibility for and protects fellow members of their group. Loyalty is paramount and overrides most other societal rules. In these societies, offense leads to shame and loss of face

Motivation towards Achievement and Success

With an intermediate score of 45, North Macedonia has a bit of both worlds: high Motivation towards Achievement and Success for certain parts and low Motivation towards Achievement and Success for others, but no clearly dominant cultural value

Uncertainty Avoidance

At 87, North Macedonia scores very high on Uncertainty Avoidance, demonstrating that as a nation they see mechanisms to avoid ambiguity. People do not readily accept change and are very risk adverse. They maintain rigid codes of belief and behaviour and are intolerant of unorthodox behaviour and ideas. To minimize the level of uncertainty, there is an emotional need for strict rules, laws, policies, and regulations.

Long Term Orientation

At a score of 35, North Macedonia exhibits a relatively normative instead of pragmatic. People in such societies have a strong concern with establishing the absolute Truth; they are normative in their thinking. They exhibit great respect for traditions, a relatively small propensity to save for the future, and a focus on achieving quick results.

Indulgence

The low score of 35 in this dimension shows that North Macedonia has a culture of restraint. Restrained societies have a tendency toward cynicism and pessimism. Also, they do not put much emphasis on leisure time and control the gratification of their desires. People have the perception that their actions are restrained by social norms and feel that indulging themselves is somewhat wrong.

Source: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/country-comparison/>

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